

Novel Method in Synthesis of 3-Phenyl-4-styryl- and 3-Phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarins. Formation of 3-Phenylacetic Acid Benzisoxazole from 3-Phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin and $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ †

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2'-Hydroxychalcone (1) is esterified with phenylacetic acid in presence of phosphorous oxychloride in pyridine to get 2'-phenylacetylchalcone (2). 2 on Baker - Venkataraman transformation (BVT) in KOH - pyridine instead of giving β -diketone or γ -chromone derivative gave 3-phenyl-4-styrylcoumarin (3). Similarly, methylsalicylate on esterification with phenylacetic acid gave 2-phenylacetyloxymethyl salicylate (4) which on BVT gave 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (5). 5 with $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ in ethanol gave 3-phenylacetic acid benzisoxazole (6). The identity was confirmed by chemical reactions, analytical and uv, ir and nmr spectral data.

In earlier communication, a new synthesis of 3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin was reported¹. Coumarins have varied useful properties². The preparations of 4-styryl-6-methylcoumarin is reported³ from 6-methyl-4-acetic acid-coumarin by condensation with aldehyde in pyridine at 130° , 2'-hydroxychalcone on condensation with Wittig reagent⁴, $\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CHCOOEt}$ form 4-styrylcoumarin⁵ and 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin from α -methoxy, coumarone⁶. The latter is also formed by heating phenol with phenylmalonic ester⁷ by cyclisation of methyl chloroformate of deoxybenzoin with ethylchloroformate⁸ or methylformate in potassium

carbonate - DMSO, or by the action of BF_3 etherate on aurone epoxide⁹.

The present work reports a new route for the synthesis of 3-phenyl-4-styrylcoumarins and 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarins. The chalcone (1) with phenylacetic acid in presence of phosphorous oxychloride formed an ester (2), which on BVT using pulverised potassium hydroxide in pyridine gave compound 3.

Compound 3 did not give colour reaction with neutral ferric chloride solution indicating the absence of free phenolic hydroxyl group and hence the involvement of phenolic OH group in cyclisation forming a heterocyclic compound. 3 can either be a coumarin (3) or chromone derivative. An intermediate β -diketone is not formed, hence the chromone derivative is not possible. Again even if the β -diketone is formed as an intermediate, there is no H-atom on the carbon atom flanked by two carbonyl groups unabling the cyclisation to chromone. So it gave the only possibility of the formation of a coumarin ring. When 2'-phenylacetyloxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalcone was put to BVT, 3-phenyl-4-styryl-6-methylcoumarin was obtained. 3 gave fluorescence in dilute solution and exhibited characteristic uv absorption peaks (λ_{max} 284). 3 also gave test for unsaturation (Baeyer's test). The compounds 3a - e are listed in Table 1. As there is double bond conjugation in 3-phenylcoumarins which have stilbene structure, possess oestrogenic activity; the substitution at 4-position with styryl group can enhance this activity and preliminary results in this direction are encouraging. Methyl salicylate was esterified at phenolic OH position with phenylacetic acid to get 2-phenylacetyloxy-

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TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA 3-PHENYL-4-STYRYL-COUMARINS (3)*

Compd.	Chalcone (1)	Ester (2) M p. (°C)	Coumarins (3)	M.p. (°C)
a	2'-OH-5'-Me-4-OCH ₃	85	3-Ph-6-Me(p-OCH ₃)styryl	169
b	2'-OH-4-OCH ₃	94	3-Ph-4(p-OCH ₃)styryl	155
c	2'-OH	91	3-Ph-4-styryl	165
d	2'-OH-5'-Me-	81	3-Ph-6-Me-4-styryl	171
e	2'-OH-5'-Cl-4-OCH ₃	61	3-Ph-6-Cl-4-(p-OCH ₃)styryl	185

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

methyl salicylate (4) which on BVT gave 3-phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (5). The formation of 5 can be explained by intramolecular aldol condensation. The condensation follows by elimination of a water molecule, forming coumarin (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The coumarin (5) revealed λ_{max} 320 and 284 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 000 (OH), 3 010 (ArH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 560, 1 430, 1 370, 1 280, 1 150, 960 and 830 cm^{-1} . 3-Phenyl-4-hydroxycoumarin (5) was condensed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanol by refluxing in a water-bath for 4 h. The product (6) obtained was not coumarin hydroxylamine as reported earlier in the reaction of 4-hydroxycoumarin with hydroxylamine hydrochloride¹⁰. 4 gave acid test (COOH) and compared well with benzisoxazole derivatives 6a was found to be 3-phenylacetic acid-1,2-benzisoxazole¹¹. The reaction is represented in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

5-Nitromethylsalicylate under the conditions for the preparations of 4-6, gave 5-nitro-3-phenylacetic acid-benzisoxazole.

Experimental

The chalcones⁷ (1a-e) were prepared by condensing ketone with aldehyde following Claisen-Smidt condensation.

The ester (2) : The chalcone (1 ; 0.01 mol) and phenylacetic acid (0.01 mol) were dissolved in pyridine (20 ml) and POCl₃ (2.5 ml) was added dropwise to the solution with stirring. The mixture was kept for 1 h and diluted with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water, dilute bicarbonate solution and again with water and dried to yield the esters (2a-e).

The coumarins (3a-e) : The ester (2 ; 0.01 mol) was added to pulverised KOH (1.5 g) in pyridine (15 ml) and the mixture was kept for 2 h. It was then decomposed with dilute HCl. The resulting yellow solid was washed in turn with water, bicarbonate solution and water, and crystallised to yield the products (80-100%).

The salicylate (4a-b) : 1a-b (0.05 mol) and phenylacetic acid (0.05 mol) were dissolved in pyridine (20 ml) and POCl₃ (3 ml) added dropwise to the solution with constant stirring. The mixture was kept for 1 h, then acidified with dilute HCl in crushed ice. The resulting white solid was washed in turn with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and crystallised from ethanol to get the esters (70%) : 4a, m.p. 56° and 4b, m.p. 71°. Compound 4 did not give colour with neutral ferric chloride.

4-Hydroxycoumarin (5a-b) : The ester (4a-b ; 0.01 mol) was added to pulverised KOH (1.5 g) in pyridine (15 ml) and the mixture was kept for 2 h. The resulting white solid was washed in turn with water, bicarbonate solution and water, and crystallised from ethanol to get the products (40-60%) : 5a, m.p. 230°, 5b, m.p. 102°.

Condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin (5a, b) with NH₂OH.HCl. Formation of 3-phenylacetic acid-1,2 benzisoxazole (6a, b) : A mixture of 5a, b (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) and NH₂OH.HCl (0.02 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The solution on dilution with water gave a solid which was crystallised from ethanol to get the products : 6a, m.p. 265°, eq. wt. 253 ; 6b, m.p. 100° eq. wt. 298.

References

- P. D. LOKHANDE and B. J. GHIYA, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, communicated.
- T. O. SOINE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1964, 53, 231.
- A. MUSTAFA, M. KAMEL, M. A. ALLAM, A. H. E. HARHAS and A. HASSAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 76, 5011.
- G. WITTIG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88.
- U. K. JOSHI, R. M. KELKAR and M. V. PARADKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect B*, 1983, 22, 1151.
- A. C. JAIN, V. K. ROHOTAGI and T. R. SHESHADRI, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 499.
- C. MENTZER, D. MOLHO and P. VENIER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1949, 749.
- A. C. JAIN and S. M. JAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 106.
- M. GEOOHEGAM, W. E. O. SULLIVAN and E. M. PHILBIN, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 22, 3209.
- G. CASINI, F. GANLTIEN and M. L. STEIN, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1969, 6, 729.
- A. R. KATRIZKY and C. W. REES, "Comprehensive Heterocyclic Chemistry", Pergamon, Oxford, 1984, Vol. 6, p. 118.
- A. G. DOSHI and B. J. GHIYA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1986, 55, 502.